

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE NONLINEAR BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE PANELS

by Dr W. M. BANKS

*Department of Mechanics of Materials
University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, U.K.*

The nonlinear behaviour of composite panels fabricated using unidirectional reinforcements and subjected to uniaxial in-plane loading has been considered by the author at the two previous ICCM Conferences (1) and (2) from a theoretical viewpoint. The analysis involved the solution of the von Karman type large deflection equation for orthotropic plates in addition to the consideration of the energy in the buckled plate system. Various boundary conditions on the unloaded edges were considered together with simply supported loaded ends.

A parallel experimental investigation has been carried out to validate the theoretical findings. This involved the fabrication and testing of orthotropic plates in the form of glass reinforced plastic using unidirectional reinforcement.

The test set-up gave simply supported flexural boundary conditions on all edges and permitted the testing of plates with various aspect ratios. Large deflection results and post critical stress distributions were obtained for plates with constant in-plane displacement on the loaded ends and stress free unloaded edges.

The paper gives details of how the test specimens were prepared and of the plate testing equipment used. The experimental results for large deflections and postcritical stress distributions are compared with theory.

NOTATION

a, b	panel dimensions in x and y directions respectively
D_{11} , D_{22}	flexural rigidity of plate per unit width for bending about the y and x axes respectively, given by $D_{11} = E_{11}h^3/12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}), \quad D_{22} = E_{22}h^3/12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$
E_{11} , E_{22}	modulus of elasticity in the x and y directions respectively
G_{12}	elastic shear modulus in x-y plane
h	plate thickness
P, P_{cr}	applied load and critical load respectively in x direction
u, u_{cr}	in-plane displacement and critical value of in-plane displacement of the plate middle surface in the x direction
w	out-of-plane deflections
w_0	initial out-of-plane deflection without load
ν_{12} , ν_{21}	Poisson's ratio in the x and y directions respectively
σ_{cr}	critical buckling stress
σ_x^b , σ_y^b	bending stresses in the x and y directions respectively
σ_x^m , σ_y^m	direct membrane stresses in the x and y directions respectively

INTRODUCTION

Several idealised forms of orthotropic plates have been used in the past. With modern composite fibre-reinforced systems, it is possible to fabricate the material and final plate structure in one operation with some control on the final properties of the plate. In particular, where the reinforcement is based on unidirectionally aligned fibres, the resulting structure is orthotropic and homogeneous, and such plates form an excellent basis for testing the validity of orthotropic plate theory. Because of the nature of the test specimens their fabrication is first considered before the test equipment is described.

PREPARATION OF TEST SPECIMENS

The composite orthotropic plates shown schematically in Fig.1 were fabricated using unidirectional glass fibre laminate and a polyester resin matrix in a hand lay-up process. The glass fibre was 'E-type Tyglas' and the polyester resin was 'Crystic 272' supplied by Scott Bader Co Ltd. The properties of the constituent materials provided by the manufacturers are given in Table 1. The 'Crystic 272' resin was chosen because it is a high performance isophthalic resin with relatively high mechanical strength, widely used for applications in structural engineering. The chemical reaction which produced hardening of the resin was initiated by the addition of an appropriate catalyst and accelerator.

The plates were fabricated using a hand lay up vacuum process which was originally devised at the Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough. A detailed

FIG. 1. CO-ORDINATE AXES AND SIGN CONVENTION.

description of this process is given in (3). Plates and test specimens of very consistent properties, and of very high quality were obtained.

TABLE 1
Properties of the constituent materials of the composite

Material	Modulus of elasticity GNm^{-2}	Poisson's ratio	Specific gravity
E-glass ^a	72.4	0.22	2.56
Polyester resin ^a (Crystic 272)	3.66	0.3 - 0.36 ^b	1.21

^a Values obtained from manufacturer

^b Value when post-cured

THE PLATE-TESTING EQUIPMENT

The plates were tested in a rig which fitted into a Tinius Olsen compression-tension universal testing machine. To obtain the stress distribution in the post-buckled plate a series of strain gauge investigations were undertaken.

A general outline of the plate-testing rig is given in Fig.2. It was designed and built by Fok (4) and is similar in many respects to an earlier rig described by Hoff et al (5). Minor alterations were incorporated to enable the testing of various aspect ratios in the glass-reinforced plastic plates. The rig was designed to give a uniform displacement along the loaded edges, stress-free unloaded edges and simply supported flexural boundary conditions. It was designed to test plates 250 mm wide with various lengths, up to a maximum aspect ratio of 2.

The rig consisted essentially of a lower base, an easily removable upper platen and two identical side supports. The side supports were rigidly bolted to the lower base through a plate welded to the channel sections, and the upper platen was constrained to move vertically as the panel was compressed. The load was applied to the specimen through a series of needle bearings mounted in steel blocks, which were guided into the platens. This ensured the closest approximations to a simply supported loaded edge. The diameter of the bearings was 14.3 mm and that of the individual needles was 3.17 mm.

FIG. 2. PLATE TESTING RIG.

The upper platen had four 50 mm x 50 mm T-sections rigidly attached to it to ensure vertical movement when the load was applied. The inside edges were machined to align with the machined outer edges of the side supports with a tolerance of 0.05 mm. The side supports were made from 127 mm x 63.5 mm structural channel, with a web thickness of 6.35 mm. A plate was welded to the bottom of the channel and the assembly was machined to ensure that the lower surface was flat and perpendicular to the web of the channel. Slotted holes in the channels permitted the knife edges to be moved to accommodate variations in plate thickness. Dowels on the side channels ensured that the knife edges were held vertically.

The knife edges were machined from steel bar and rounded off at the edges to a radius of 4.75 mm. They provided line contact along the length of the plate. During tests they were adequately lubricated to prevent restraint on the panel and to permit it to rotate freely about the edges.

The tests were carried out in a Tinius Olsen tension-compression testing machine with a maximum capacity of around 0.9 MN and a minimum resolution of approximately 9 N. The loading was displacement-controlled and was measured through the base of the machine by load transducers.

TEST METHOD

To initiate a test, the panel was positioned in the testing rig by removing the top platen and sliding the plate in until the bottom of the plate rested on the slotted rods in the base. Since irregularity in thickness along the edges of the plate is inevitable with GRP laminates, the method proposed for positioning the knife edges by Hoff et al (5) was adopted, i.e. the knife edges were positioned against the panel to contact at the thickest points, and tentatively clamped. Having confirmed that the plate was not too rigid (in which case some of the load would have been lost in friction between the supports and the plate) the knife edges were fully tightened and the upper platen fixed in position.

Having positioned dial gauges as appropriate the plate was subjected to a small load of approximately 0.1 of the buckling load. This served to 'settle' the plate into the test rig and to take up any movement between the components of the rig. This load was then removed until only a very small load registered on the machine. The dial gauges and strain gauges were then zeroed and the loading increased in appropriate increments until collapse of the plate occurred. Since the testing machine was displacement-controlled, collapse was noted as a sudden reduction in load.

Using this approach a series of 18 preliminary tests were conducted to provide some initial experience. Several plates were then strain gauged to give detailed strain distributions and to permit comparison with theoretical predictions. The results from one plate only are presented for brevity.

In this case gauges were placed on both sides of one symmetrical half (see Fig.3). The aspect ratio of this plate was chosen to give the minimum buckling load

**FIG. 3. STRAIN GAUGE LAYOUT ON PLATE No.2
WITH ASPECT RATIO OF 1.3575**

for the plate properties, which were ascertained before machining. The value of 1.3575 was derived from the formula (6),

$$\frac{a}{b} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}}$$

With this value, it was ensured that the plate would buckle into one half-wave and so the gauges could be positioned centrally. Both the membrane and bending stresses could be ascertained and these were used as a basis for comparison with the theoretical predictions. In addition, the out-of-plane deflections were recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results are presented and compared with the theoretical work referred to earlier. The large deflection behaviour is described first; this is followed by the stress distributions for increasing load and within the plate for various specified load ratios.

Large Deflection Behaviour

The large deflection behaviour is considered in relation to both in-plane and out-of-plane movement. The ability to predict deflections accurately is important since the redistribution of post-buckling stress and the change in axial stiffness are dependent on the derivatives of these deflections.

Load-end displacement behaviour

In this section, results from tests on 2 plates taken from a large series of tests are presented. To enable realistic displacement readings to be recorded,

Plate No.	E_{11} GNm ⁻²	E_{22} GNm ⁻²	G_{12} GNm ⁻²	ν_{12}	a/b	h mm	σ_{cr} (theoretical) MNm ⁻²
1	29.80	6.30	2.06	0.33	1	2.489	3.905
2	27.38	8.06	2.71	0.33	1.3575 ^a	2.667	4.266
3	25.60	4.47	2.30	0.33	2 ^b	2.565	3.595
4	6.30	29.80	2.06	0.07	1	2.489	3.905
5	5.35	29.35	2.19	0.06	0.5	2.578	3.531

^a Chosen to give minimum buckling load

^b Buckled into two half-waves (all others into one half-wave)

TABLE 2
Material properties of test plates

rectangular plates with an aspect ratio of 2 were tested initially. These plates were approximately 0.5 m long and had a critical strain of around 130×10^{-6} . This meant that the maximum deflection at the critical load was of the order 0.065 mm.

The results are presented in Figs.4 and 5; in each case the full lines are

FIG. 4. LOAD-END DISPLACEMENT CURVES FOR
PLATE No.3. BUCKLED IN 2 HALF WAVES.

FIG 5. LOAD-END DISPLACEMENT CURVE FOR PLATE No.4.

derived from theory. The plate properties are given in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, the plates were cut from four different fabrications. In all cases the plates buckled into one half-wave in the longitudinal direction except for plate No.3 which buckled into two half-waves.

In Fig.4 the result for the plate which buckled into two half-waves is presented. The post-buckling stiffness is low and it is seen that the experimental results again follow the trend closely. As well as loading in the major stiffness direction, tests were carried out with the load applied in the minor stiffness direction. The results of one of these tests (plate No.4) are given in Fig.5.

The results show that the post-buckling stiffness can be accurately predicted and, provided due care is taken with the experimental readings, fair correlation is obtained with the theory.

Load-out-of-plane deflection behaviour

The out-of-plane deflection results are presented in Figs. 6 and 7 for plates loaded in the major stiffness direction, and in Figs.8 and 9 for plates loaded in the minor stiffness direction.

FIG.6. LOAD OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION CURVES FOR PLATE 1

FIG. 7. LOAD OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION CURVES FOR PLATE 2.

FIG. 8. LOAD OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION CURVES FOR PLATE 4. LOADED IN MINOR STIFFNESS DIRECTION

FIG. 9. LOAD OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION CURVES FOR PLATE 5 LOADED IN MINOR STIFFNESS DIRECTION.

For plates loaded in the major stiffness direction the deviation of the experimental results from those for a perfect plate increased as the aspect ratio was increased. This is due mainly to the difficulty in fabricating the plates and the resulting imperfections. This deviation from the perfectly flat plate behaviour will occur in practical applications. The author has extended the theoretical work referred to earlier to take account of initial imperfections (see e.g. ref (2)). To obtain a comparison with this imperfect plate theory a value for the initial deviation from flatness was chosen so that the early part of the theoretical curve matched the experimental results. The 'imperfect' curves are included in the figures. It can be seen that, provided the initial imperfection is known, the experimental points conform more closely with the 'imperfect' curves. The initial imperfection value required to provide a correlation is approximately 0.5 of the plate thickness for the lower aspect ratios. This is quite a large initial deviation from flatness.

For the plates loaded in the minor stiffness direction, the deflections, as expected, are seen to be much larger (Figs.8 and 9). As before the 'imperfect' results are also presented; at the higher load ratios the deviations from the theoretical results are considerable.

STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS

The strain gauge lay-out and other details of the plate used for the stress distribution studies is given in Fig.3. Stress variations are presented for increasing load for particular areas of important stress values. In addition, the distribution of stress across the plate is presented for selected load ratios in the post buckled regime.

The results are presented in Figs.10 to 16. The effects of increasing the load on the stress levels are shown in Figs.10 to 12. The variations of longitudinal membrane and bending stresses are shown in Fig.10. The membrane stress values follow the theoretical predictions very closely while the imperfect-plate solution for the bending stress is again in moderately good agreement with the experimental results, particularly at the lower load ratios. The transverse membrane and bending stresses given in Fig.11 also agree reasonably well with the theoretical predictions.

It was not possible to compare the theoretical and experimental membrane stresses at the unloaded edge because of the difficulty of strain gauging close to

FIG. 10. DISTRIBUTIONS OF LONGITUDINAL MEMBRANE AND BENDING STRESSES AT CENTRE OF PLATE 2.

FIG. 11. DISTRIBUTIONS OF TRANSVERSE MEMBRANE AND BENDING STRESSES AT CENTRE OF PLATE 2

FIG. 12. DISTRIBUTION OF MEMBRANE STRESS NEAR UNLOADED EDGE OF PLATE 2.

FIG. 13. MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AT BUCKLE CREST IN PLATE 2 FOR $P/P_{cr} = 2.0$.

FIG. 14. BENDING STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS IN PLATE 2
FOR $P/P_{cr} = 2.0$.

FIG. 15. MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AT BUCKLE
CREST IN PLATE 2 FOR $P/P_{cr} = 2.53$.

$$\underline{P/P_{Cr} = 2.53}$$

**FIG. 16. BENDING STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS IN
PLATE FOR $P/P_{Cr} = 2.53$.**

the support. Instead a comparison is made in Fig.12 of the membrane stress values for a distance in from the edge equal to 10% of the plate width. The correlation is seen to be very good, particularly up to a post-buckling load ratio of 2.0.

The membrane and bending stress distributions across the centre of the plate for P/P_{Cr} of 2.0 are shown in Figs.13 and 14 respectively. The membrane stresses are in excellent agreement with those predicted except for the values very close to the edge. The transverse membrane stress σ_y^m was very much smaller than the longitudinal value, and of opposite sign. The bending stress distributions shown in Fig. 14 do not show the same good correlation, although the trends are predicted. The transverse bending stress σ_y^b is of particular interest. The maximum theoretical value is away from the centre towards the edge and this is clearly corroborated by the experimental results. A localised effect at the edge is evident in the change in sign of the bending stress. This would appear to be due to a change in curvature near the support which also affects the stress levels some small distance from it.

At the higher level of load ratio of 2.53, the same trends are apparent. The correlation for the membrane stress distributions shown in Fig.15 is much better than for the bending stress distributions shown in Fig.16. Moreover, the bending stress distributions do not correspond as well with the theoretical predictions as at the lower load ratio (Fig.14). The change in deflected form as the load ratio is increased affects the levels as well as the evident contribution near the supports. It is clearly more difficult to predict the bending stress distributions with accuracy than the membrane stress values, particularly near the edges as the load ratio is increased. The edges are the area of smallest bending moment and it is, therefore, not so important that these should be predicted accurately. At the areas of highest bending stress levels the correlation is reasonable.

Stress levels in the immediate post-buckling regime can thus be predicted with some confidence. Even at the higher levels the membrane distributions correlate well with the theoretical analysis, but care has to be taken in predicting the bending stress levels, particularly at the higher loads. Figures 14 and 16 show that the maximum predicted bending stresses are some 20% higher than the

corresponding experimental values and are thus conservative. Indeed, all the high stress values are overestimated. From the results presented it is seen that the theoretical predictions would include an additional factor of safety if used on a design basis.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The experimental work reported here made possible an evaluation of the previous theoretical analyses. To the author's knowledge only a limited number of experimental results on homogeneous orthotropic plates subjected to in-plane loading have been published to date. Several results have been produced for idealised systems such as corrugated sheeting, etc. but these, while providing an overall picture, necessarily fall short at localised points of discontinuity in the structure. Composite material in the form of glass-reinforced plastic provides an excellent base for evaluating orthotropic plate theory.

It is difficult to fabricate composite plates by a hand lay-up process to very high quality. The vacuum process adopted and described, eliminated this problem to some extent. Curing, however, still gives difficulty and in spite of precautions, initial imperfections are always present. Similar fabrication and curing problems are encountered in practice.

The testing facilities reproduced the assumed boundary conditions although some restraint was evident from the experimental results at the unloaded edges. In general, realistic comparisons could be made. It was difficult to obtain some of the deflection readings accurately due to the small magnitudes involved. The end displacement behaviour had to be monitored carefully because of this problem. The out-of-plane deflections were larger and more accuracy was possible in this case.

The experimental results, in general, confirm the theoretical predictions, in many cases up to three times the buckling load, for the glass-reinforced plastic plates considered. The experimental large deflection behaviour also confirms the theoretical predictions to a reasonable degree. In particular the post-buckling stiffness is seen to agree favourably with that obtained from the readings. The agreement between the theoretical and experimental out-of-plane deflections was improved when initial imperfections were taken into account.

The stress distributions presented in Figs.10 - 16 show that in all cases the predictions overestimate the experimental stresses. The membrane stress distributions remain very accurate even up to a post-buckling load ratio of 2.5. The bending distributions are less so, giving a value of 20% less than that predicted at the higher levels for the most important positions on the plate. The predicted stress levels could thus be used with confidence in design.

Experimental confirmation of the theoretical analysis for stress-free unloaded edges gives confidence in the analysis for application to other boundary conditions. The geometric non-linear behaviour of composite systems is going to play an increasingly important role as these structures find wider applications with the increasing demands of modern technology. It is therefore necessary to be able to predict their behaviour with confidence.

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